

OF SOME DEFORMABLE BODIES MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

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Abstract: Information is given on the structure of single deformable solids, strength of materials, elongation diagram, plasticity of materials, brittleness of materials, hardness of materials.

Key words: Force, deformation, substance, elastic, plastic, energy, work, displacement, elongation, volume, surface, displacement.

Deformation of a solid body is a change in size and shape of a body under the influence of external forces, when it is heated or cooled.

If the body completely recovers its initial state after being subjected to deformation in a deformable environment, it is called elastic deformation, and if it does not recover, it is called plastic deformation. Materials have elasticity and plastic properties. For example, steel, rubber, skin-elastic, wax-plastic materials.

Relative deformation. Most of the deformations are of two types: stretching and compression deformations. Let's get acquainted with these deformations.

Similar to the long sturgeon $\vec{F}_1$ va $\vec{F}_2$ forces are applied. $\vec{F}_1 = \vec{F}_2 = \vec{F}$ just because it was F we consider that the force has been applied. The result is sturgeon Δl extends to. Usually, the mast is taken with a positive sign when it is stretched, and a negative sign when it moves (Figure 1).

$\vec{F}_1$

(Figure 1).

The force per unit cross-sectional area is called tension.

$$\sigma = \frac{F}{S} \quad (1)$$

The concept of relative deformation is introduced as a quantitative description of the degree of deformation.

Longitudinal (warping) relative deformation

$$\varepsilon = \frac{\Delta l}{l} \quad (2),$$

transverse (compression) relative deformation

$$\varepsilon^I = \frac{\Delta d}{d} \quad (3)$$

defined using expressions. The following relationship exists among them

$$\varepsilon^I = -\mu\varepsilon,$$

μ - depends on the properties of the substance, it is called Poisson's ratio.

Hooke's law for solid deformation. English physicist Hooke's relative elongation for small deformations ε and voltage σ determines the existence of the following relationships between:

$$\sigma = E * \varepsilon \quad (4)$$

$$\varepsilon = \frac{\Delta l}{l} = \frac{1}{E} \sigma \quad (5)$$

E is called the Young's modulus. the larger it is, the less the body is deformed. $\frac{\Delta l}{l} = 1$ ga $E = \sigma$ will be. So, Young's modulus is equal to the stress that causes unit relative deformation of the body:

$$\varepsilon = \frac{F}{ES} \quad (6)$$

or Hooke's law can be written differently using the last expression

$$F = \frac{ES}{l} \Delta l = k \Delta l \quad (7)$$

In elastic deformation, the amount of deformation is proportional to the deformable force. Here it is called k-elasticity coefficient.

Students should be told that the deformation of a rigid body obeys Hooke's law up to a certain limit.

Deformation and solid structure. As a result of deformation, the particles located at the nodes of the crystal lattice move relative to each other. This leads to a violation of the balance of forces of interaction between particles. As a result, there are internal elastic forces that try to return the particles to their original positions F_{el} occurs.

It should be noted that for any deformation, work is done or heat is given. Therefore, the change in work energy of a deformed body is equal to the amount of work done or given heat under the influence of external forces.

For example, the potential energy of an elastically stretched or compressed string changes as follows.

$$E_n = A = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \frac{ES}{l} (\Delta l)^2 \quad (8)$$

Here A – the work of the external forces that made this deformation; S – cross-sectional surface of a deformable body, l - length, E - wool module. It can be seen that the potential energy of an elastically stretched rod is the square of the deformation $(\Delta l)^2$ to'gri proporsional ekanligi kelib chiqadi.

References

1. G'aniyev.A.G. Fizika(AI va KHK uchundarslik) 1-qism "O'qituvchi" nashriyoti Toshkent-2012 yil.
2. Ninitin.E.M Nazariy mexanika (texnikumlar uchun darslik) "O'qituvchi " nashriyoti Toshkent-1970 yil
3. Варвак.П.М., Варвак Л.П. Метод сеток в задачах расчета строительных конструкций. – М.: Стройиздат, 1977. –160 с.
4. Иванов В.Н. Вариационные принципы и методы решения задач теории упругости. – М.: Изд-во РУДН, 2001. – 176 с.
5. Игамбердиев, Х. Х., & Турдалиев, З. С. (2021). Формирование новаторских изобретательских навыков студентов. In *Прорывные научные исследования: проблемы, пределы и возможности* (pp. 99-102).
6. Saddin o'g'li, T. Z., & Nurmuxammadovich, P. N. M. (2022). МАТЕМАТИКА DARSLARINI SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHDA SHARQ MUTAFFAKKIRLARINING O'RNI. *ИЖТИМОЙ ФАНЛАРДА ИННОВАЦИЯ ОНЛАЙН ИЛМИЙ ЖУРНАЛИ*, 2(3), 34-36.
7. Парсаева, Н. Ж., Курбанов, З. Х., & Бобокулова, Ш. (2021). Исследование физико-механических свойств бетонных изделий используемые промышленные отходы. *Science and Education*, 2(5), 417-423.
8. Хакимов, О. М., Курбанов, З. Х., & Мухаммедов, Ф. (2021). Реализация возможностей получения легких наполнителей на основе меньше пластиковых почв в нашей республике. *Science and Education*, 2(5), 176-181.
9. Курбанов, З. Х., & угли Холбоев, С. О. (2021). Микроарматурализация сухих строительных смесей волластонитом. *Science and Education*, 2(5), 410-416.
10. Курбанов, З. Х., & Сулайманов, Ж. Ж. (2021). Подготовка зданий к отделке местными материалами из натурального камня. *Science and Education*, 2(5), 403-409.
11. Курбанов, З. Х., Мамиров, А. Х., & Махкамов, М. З. У. (2021).

Улучшение процесса горения керамической плитки на заводе строительных материалов. *Science and Education*, 2(5), 395-402.

12. Парсаева, Н. Ж., Курбанов, З. Х., & Расулова, Н. Б. (2021). Технология производства земляных работ с применением геосеток. *Science and Education*, 2(12), 324-333.

13. Khamidulloevich, K. Z., Begalievich, A. K., & Sanjarbek, K. (2021). TECHNOLOGY OF PRODUCTION OF EARTH WORKS WITH THE APPLICATION OF GEOGRAPHS. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 1(5), 267-271.

14. Курбанов, З. Х., Ганиев, А., & Усанова, Г. А. (2022). ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ СОСТАВА СУХОЙ СТРОИТЕЛЬНОЙ СМЕСИ НА ОСНОВЕ МРАМОРНЫХ ОТХОДОВ. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 2(1), 299-304.

15. Ганиев, А., Курбанов, З. Х., Усанова, Г. А., & Назаров, Ж. Ж. Ў. (2022). Тоғ-кон саноати чиқиндилари асосида олинадиган майда донали бетонлар. *Science and Education*, 3(3), 258-263.

16. Ganiev, A., Tursunov, B. A., & Kurbanov, Z. K. (2022). Prospects for the use of multiple vermiculitis. *Science and Education*, 3(4), 409-414.

17. Kurbanov, Z., & Parsaeva, N. (2022, June). Strong grinding based on local raw materials getting stones. In *AIP Conference Proceedings* (Vol. 2432, No. 1, p. 030104). AIP Publishing LLC.

18. Ганиев, А., угли Турсунов, Б. А., & Курбанов, З. Х. (2022). Особо легких бетонов полученных на основе сельского хозяйственных отходов. *Science and Education*, 3(4), 492-498.

19. Nurmamatov, N. R. (2022). Bazalt armatura ishlab chiqarishdagi chiqindi asosida fibrabeton tarkibini tanlash va xossalarini o'rganish. *Science and Education*, 3(3), 146-152.

20. Nurmamatov, N. R., & Tilavov, E. N. O. G. L. (2022). Bazalt tolasi

asosida fibrabeton optimal tarkibini tanlash va fizik mexanik xossalarini taxlili. *Science and Education*, 3(3), 153-160.

21. Istamov, Y., & O'roqboyev, O. B. (2022). YUQORI MUSTANKAM BETONLAR OLISHDA KIMYOVIY VA MINERAL QO'SHIMCHALAR YORDAMIDA FIZIK-MEXANIK XOSSALLARINI TADQIQ ETISH. *Журнал интегрированного образования и исследований*, 1(1), 310-318.

22. Нурмаматов, Н. Р. (2022). Изучение процесса получения пенобетона на основе местного синтетического сырья. *Science and Education*, 3(3), 291-295.

23. Баходиров, А. А., & Абдусаматов, К. Б. (2020). перспективы использования асбестоцементных отходов в качестве микрофибры при производстве газобетона. *IEJRD-Международный междисциплинарный журнал*, 5(7), 5.

24. Абдусаматов, К. Б. (2022). Исследовательская работа по определению теплопроводности и термическое сопротивление образцов газобетона. *Science and Education*, 3(3), 244-248.

25. Begalievich, A. K., & Abdulazizovich, B. A. (2022). Efficiency of Obtaining Wall Materials from Industrial Waste. *International Journal of Formal Education*, 1(7), 134-139.